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**Evaluating the Determinants of Crude Oil
Prices in the United Kingdom**

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Abstract

This paper assesses the main determinants of crude oil prices, using data from the United Kingdom (UK) to estimate the impact of Brexit and COVID-19. The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach is applied to monthly time series data from January 2001 to December 2022, allowing for the simultaneous estimation of long- and short-run effects. The estimation also uses an iterative nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) approach to account for asymmetries among the data, providing new insights into the determinants of crude oil prices. To compare between different periods of uncertainty, three models are assessed: one pre-Brexit and COVID-19, one during Brexit, and one during COVID-19. The results have key implications for UK policymakers and traders alike, highlighting the importance of country-specific analyses in determining crude oil prices.

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1 Introduction

Crude oil has dominated the global energy mix since c.1965 (Stevens, 2018; Ritchie, 2024) due to its high energy density (Layton, 2008) and versatility (Wu, 2019); being essential in both transportation and petrochemical industries. Renou-Massiant (2019) finds significant evidence to suggest oil prices have been a key driver of inflation since 1991, meaning that understanding the determinants of crude oil prices is essential for policymakers. Furthermore, oil prices have fluctuated significantly over the last few decades with new economic shocks, like Brexit and COVID-19, altering short- and long-run market dynamics. Therefore, continual updates to research on the determinants of crude oil prices are needed to navigate the evolving market landscape. This dissertation aims to contribute to the existing literature by updating the research and introducing further insights in the following three ways.

Firstly, the ARDL approach of Pesaran et al. (2001) is applied, assessing the short- and long-run impacts of exogenous variables on oil prices, alongside the NARDL framework of Shin et al. (2014). NARDL models capture asymmetric relationships between variables, thus enhancing previous studies that often assume linearity. While Salem et al. (2022) share a similar aim, this dissertation extends their NARDL methodology by incorporating an iterative framework to more effectively identify the model best fitting the data. Secondly, this study aims to apply the results directly to the UK by using UK-specific data and Brent crude oil prices, considering their geographical relevance. Specifically, the impacts of Brexit and COVID-19 are examined, thus filling a gap in the literature concerning the UK's oil market dynamics amidst periods of economic stress. Finally, this study reports CUSUM tests and dynamic multiplier graphs to assess robustness and provide further results.

2 Oil Markets

This section provides a background to oil markets, explaining the growing influence of oil market financialisation and the UK's position as a net importer.

2.1 Historical Environment

The dynamics of oil markets have evolved extensively since 1859, when Edwin Drake drilled the first commercial oil well in the US (Dickey, 1959). Historically, oil markets were mainly physical markets, meaning that newly discovered oil fields throughout the late 19th and early 20th centuries were key drivers of oil prices. Some of the most notable discoveries included the Spindletop Gusher (House, 1946) and oil in Saudi Arabia (Long, 1979).

For the first half of the 20th century, the “Seven Sisters” dominated oil markets (Wood, 2016). Consisting of the seven largest oil firms at the time, the anti-competitive cartel controlled the majority of oil production, distribution and reserves. Noguera (2017) cites the “Seven Sisters” to have been vertically integrated, meaning that by the 1950s they controlled 98.3% of global petroleum production (Engen, 2009). However, throughout the 1960s and 1970s, the “Seven Sisters” market power was challenged by the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), a cartel aiming to stabilise international oil prices and safeguard member countries from exploitation (OPEC, 2021). Although OPEC was initially ineffectual (Wood, 2016), they began exerting influence over crude oil markets in 1973, triggered by the Yom Kippur War and subsequent Arab oil embargo on the United States and the Netherlands. Noguera (2017) states this led to a wave of nationalisations in oil markets, with OPEC now controlling 38% of all crude oil (Statista, 2023).

Another structural change in oil markets was the shift from prices being governed solely by physical demand. Oil market financialisation (Fattouh and Mahadeva, 2012) refers to the growing influence of financial markets and speculative trading activities on oil prices. This shift was brought about by financial players with no demand for physical oil, such as hedge funds, being able to trade oil electronically through instruments like derivatives. One of the roles of futures contracts is price discovery, meaning the price of futures is highly influential on spot crude oil price. This relationship is widely accepted in both theoretical and empirical

literature (see section 3.2). Due to financialisation, oil prices have become more volatile throughout the 21st century, now being governed by periods of significant uncertainty. For example, crude oil prices traded below \$0 in Spring 2020, following unprecedented economic uncertainty from the COVID-19 Pandemic (EIA, 2021). This was driven by a contraction in physical demand and investors panic selling futures contracts (Li et al., 2022); highlighting the impact of both physical and derivative market demand on oil prices.

The EIA's energy outlook (2023) predicts oil reserves will be depleted by the mid-2050s. This impending scarcity is likely to exert upward pressure on oil prices and encourage further development of renewable alternatives. Consequently, the continuous analysis of oil markets is crucial for policymakers.

2.2. Oil Market Landscape in the UK

The UK emerged as a significant net exporter of crude oil in the early 1980s following discoveries in the North Sea. The newfound reserves, traded as Brent Crude, were quickly established as a global pricing benchmark, solidifying the UK's role in international oil markets. However, Asif and Muneer (2007) state production from UK oil fields to have peaked in the late 1990s, quickly declining as oil reserves plummeted and domestic demand outgrew production. BP (2021) showed the UK transitioned into a net importer of crude oil by the early 2000s, with proven oil reserves falling by over 48% between 2000 and 2020. In 2020, the UK consumed approximately 1.129 million barrels of oil per day, producing 1.029 million (BP, 2021).

Historically, the UK has imported the majority of its crude oil from Norway and Russia (Donnarumma, 2022). However recent geopolitical tensions, such as Russia's invasion of Ukraine, has altered this. Donnarumma (2022) further reports that the majority of exports are sold to the Netherlands and China.

Facing depleting reserves and a commitment to achieving net zero emissions by 2050 (Burnett et al., 2023), the UK is investing in cleaner alternatives. Hence, analyses must be tailored to specific countries rather than relying on generalized studies as policies are dependent on oil reserves, government objectives, and the level of economic development. For instance,

Brazil experienced a notable increase of over 42% in oil production between 2010 and 2020 (BP, 2021), presenting a contrasting scenario to the UK and suggesting differences in their respective oil market dynamics.

3 Literature Review

This section provides a comprehensive review of the previous literature, both theoretical and empirical, by looking at each variable used in this study in-turn. Given the vast amount of research techniques used to study this topic, there appears to be no universal consensus on which variables have the largest influence on prices. Further, despite recent findings showing that country-specific analyses yield important and unique results (see Olayungbo et al., 2023), most studies use US data to proxy for the global determinants of oil prices.

3.1 Interest Rates

One of the most widely researched determinants is real interest rates, first discussed by Hotelling (1931). Hotelling's Rule suggests that commodity prices grow at a rate of return equal to the real interest rate. This rule implies that an increase in real interest rate would incentivise oil producers to increase production, thus exerting a downward pressure on crude oil prices. Akram (2009) found that when real interest rates fall there is a substantial increase in commodity prices. In particular, such interest rate changes led to oil prices exhibiting overshooting behaviour, meaning short-run effects are more pronounced. Frankel (1986) found similar conclusions by applying the framework outlined in the Dornbusch Overshooting Model (Dornbusch, 1976), finding that commodity prices are more reactive in the short-run.

Frankel (2006) later examined the effect of real interest rates on six different commodity indices using data from a range of countries. One country assessed was the UK, which showed a statistically significant inverse relationship between real interest rates and crude oil prices for five of the six indices. In contrast, Frankel and Rose (2010) could not find a statistically significant inverse relationship, a contradiction to prior research. Alquist et al. (2013) also

failed to find a statistically significant long-run relationship between real interest rate and crude oil price, but found evidence of a short-run relationship.

Arora and Tanner (2013) later employed standard Vector Autoregressive models to craft Impulse Response Functions (IRFs) and forecast error variance decompositions. Their investigation found that crude oil prices consistently reacted to short-term U.S. and international real interest rates. However, the responsiveness of oil prices to long-term real interest rates changed over time, only showing an inverse relationship if the sample included data from the mid-2000s. Arora and Tanner (2013) suggested it was likely due to financialisation altering market dynamics.

A shortcoming of most studies analysing this relationship is that they assume linearity, which is often inappropriate for modelling oil prices (Kisswani et al., 2013). Consequently, this study will expand on prior research by considering nonlinearities, aiming to provide more accurate results.

3.2 Market Speculation and Uncertainty

Research into how market speculation and uncertainty is common, especially since oil market financialisation. This relationship is best explained by Prospect Theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979), suggesting investors are more risk averse when avoiding losses than they are seeking gains. Lee and Zeng (2011) used quantile cointegrating regressions to investigate how WTI futures impact spot prices. Interestingly, they found that crude oil prices responded to shocks in 1-month futures at a quicker rate when prices are higher as losses are likely to be greater; consistent with Prospect Theory.

Several papers quantify uncertainty using the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), created by Baker et al. (2016). The index captures the level of uncertainty based on newspaper articles, recording how many include terms like “uncertainty” and “deficit”. Antonakis et al. (2014), Aloui et al. (2016), Yang (2019), and Salem et al. (2022) have used the EPU index to investigate oil price fluctuations. All studies found that higher levels of uncertainty adversely affected the economy, decreasing oil demand and ultimately prices. Notably, Salem et al. (2022) used two ARDL and NARDL models to compare the impact of the COVID-19

pandemic to a period without COVID-19. Only the COVID model revealed a statistically significant short-run EPU coefficient. This suggests that during uncertain periods, such as those influenced by COVID-19, the EPU index has a more pronounced impact on oil prices. However, their study only included data up to May 2021. This is a limitation since the effects of COVID-19 continued throughout 2021 and 2022, with daily cases peaking at the beginning of 2022 (Mathieu et al., 2020).

There are only a small number of studies that have examined the impact of COVID on crude oil, most of which took place at the beginning or during the pandemic. Algamdi et al. (2021) found a negative relationship between the COVID-19 death ratio and oil prices, using data from January 2020 to June 2020. However, Fernandes (2020) showed that oil and gas firms saw an average decline in returns of 50% across 2020 alone, which likely affected the reliability of previous studies due to sample bias. This dissertation therefore adds to the literature by considering COVID-19 data from January 2020 to December 2022.

Salem et al. (2022) also tested gold, exchange rates, futures and the OPEC reference basket price as determinants of crude oil prices. The number of significant variables found during the COVID period was higher than those not in the COVID period. This suggests oil price dynamics under large periods of uncertainty are more complex, and require further study. This dissertation extends the approach of Salem et al. (2022) by also considering the effect that Brexit had on UK economic uncertainty and crude oil prices, motivated by Breinlich et al. (2018) and Acquah-Andoh et al. (2019). Bloom et al. (2018) were the first to assess the impact of Brexit on economic uncertainty using the Decision Maker Panel. Bloom et al. (2019) later extended their study by creating the Brexit Uncertainty Index (BUI). The BUI records the share of firms reporting Brexit among their top three business concerns, showing high uncertainty (38%) after the June 2016 referendum vote. This figure rose steadily to a peak of 59% in December 2018, just after the Salzburg summit in September 2018 when the EU did not agree to the UK's terms.

Although the impact of Brexit on crude oil prices has not been directly examined in the literature, Abuzayed et al. (2022) analysed financial portfolio management strategies during Brexit. They found crude oil to be a more effective hedging strategy than gold in periods of high uncertainty, further evidence of oil market financialisation.

3.3 Exchange Rates

It is widely accepted that crude oil prices are inversely related to the US Dollar (USD). Applying basic laws of supply and demand, a depreciation in USD would increase demand for crude oil importing countries since oil becomes relatively cheaper in domestic currency (both WTI and BRENT are traded in USD). Hence demand increases, placing upward pressure on prices. Employing panel cointegration methods on data from 1980-2007, Coudert et al. (2008) found empirical evidence confirming this relationship. Akram (2009) later concluded that shocks to real exchange rates account for significant fluctuations in commodity prices across all horizon levels, also observing an inverse relationship.

Salem et al. (2022) found similar results in their ARDL models, showing long-run USD depreciation had a statistically significant inverse effect on crude oil prices in the model without COVID-19. However, their NARDL model without COVID showed evidence of a statistically significant positive relationship between USD depreciation and crude oil price, contradicting the literature. This is likely due to the unique nature of the pandemic, however, a potential explanation can be made by drawing on earlier results from Jammazi et al. (2015). They used a wavelet-based NARDL model to show significant evidence supporting both long and short-run asymmetry between exchange rates and oil prices. Notably, long-run USD depreciation had more significant effects on crude oil prices than an appreciation, implying oil prices are more reactive to a weakening dollar than a strengthening one. These results again stress the importance of using nonlinear models to analyse the determinants of crude oil price, providing additional insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders alike.

3.4 Stock Markets

Degiannakis et al. (2018) observed an increase in interest surrounding the relationship between oil prices and stock markets, reporting that Google Scholar searches for "oil and the stock market" doubled between 2007 and 2017. Historically, papers have largely investigated the impact of oil markets on stock prices, however, due to the financialisation of commodity markets (Tang and Xiong, 2012; Cheng and Xiong, 2014), bidirectional causality must be considered. By including a measure of stock market performance when modelling oil prices, Degiannakis et al. (2018) showed oil price forecasting to improve.

Yin and Yang (2016) used standard Ordinary Least Squares regression to show that stock market indicators exhibited statistically significant forecasting power of WTI oil prices between 1984 and 2013. They concluded that this power stems from the stock market's ability to predict changes in economic sentiment, indicating the existence of oil market financialisation. Chen (2014) also used a predictive regression model to yield the same conclusion. Moreover, Chen (2014) found that the success ratios of the directional forecasts based on oil-sensitive stock price indices consistently outperformed randomness, exceeding the 50% threshold across all horizons and showing strong predictive power. Finally, Deginannikis and Filis (2017) showed that the inclusion of other stock markets, including the FTSE100, improved the forecasting accuracy of oil price volatility.

3.5 Economic Activity

Many studies have sought to assess the effects of economic activity in different ways. Wang and Sun (2017) used the Structural Equation Model to find that economic activity, which they measured using the Kilian economic index, had the largest positive and statistically significant effect on crude oil price. Specifically, increasing economic growth and decreasing economic uncertainty contributed to higher oil prices, similar conclusions to those found with the EPU index. These findings are coherent with theory, since economic activity is a key driver of energy demand and therefore crude oil prices. Specifically, Wang and Sun (2017) concluded that the world's major economies are the key drivers of crude oil prices since these economies demand the greatest quantities of crude oil. Therefore, to limit price fluctuations, these economies must ensure a constant flow of oil. This offers an additional explanation as to why studying oil prices during periods of uncertainty is so important.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is regularly associated with measuring economic activity, most commonly calculated using the expenditure approach (Bulin and Baltatescu, 2015). Hamilton (2003) reported clear evidence of nonlinearity in the relationship between oil prices and GDP growth, in particular, oil price rises play a more significant role on GDP growth than oil price falls. These results are consistent with earlier work including Hamilton (1983) and Mork (1989). The negative relationship is intuitive since higher oil prices increase production costs, reducing the purchasing power of consumers and therefore exerting downward pressure on economic activity. Most recently, Charfeddine et al. (2020) extended Hamilton's (2003)

study to include data up to 2019Q4, but failed to find a significant relationship between oil price decreases and GDP growth; evidence that this relationship might be evolving.

An explanation for this can be inferred from the growing focus on a switch to green energy. As economies begin transitioning away from scarce petroleum supplies, for example Brazil's shift from an oil-based transportation system to one based on sugarcane-ethanol, crude oil prices may begin to have a smaller impact on economic activity and GDP (Solomon and Krishna, 2011). Consequently, this relationship needs regular monitoring.

4 Methodology and Models

In this section, the variables selected and the modelling techniques used are justified. Further, the equations of both the ARDL and NARDL models are written, alongside the inferential exercises used in this study. To compare results across different periods of economic uncertainty, three models are analysed:

Model 1 spans from January 2001 to August 2016, covering the period unaffected by Brexit or COVID-19.

Model 2 spans September 2016 to September 2019, assessing the impact of Brexit.

Model 3 covers January 2020 to December 2022, assessing the impact of COVID-19.

4.1 Variable Selection

The dependent variable data (Brent crude oil price) was taken from the Energy Information Administration (EIA). Brent crude was chosen due to its geographical application to the UK over alternatives such as WTI (North American) and Dubai Crude. The effects of four UK-specific variables on oil prices are assessed in each model. Due to the growing interest concerning how stock markets influence crude oil prices through financialisation, the FTSE 100 closing price is used. This index was chosen as it is often considered the major benchmark of UK stock performance. Based on prior research, this variable is expected to have a positive impact on oil prices. Following the conclusions made by Jammazi et al. (2015) and Salem et

al. (2022) about the importance of exchange rates in determining oil prices, the GBP/USD exchange rate is also included. Since the UK is a net importer of crude oil (BP, 2021), this variable is predicted to have a positive effect on crude oil prices because an appreciation of Sterling increases the UK's purchasing power, increasing demand and therefore prices.

To capture the effects of market uncertainty, the UK EPU index is used. Based on the literature, this variable is expected to have an inverse relationship with crude oil price. Finally, the UK real interest rate is included due to the relevance of Hotelling's Rule in determining crude oil prices. Following this rule, real interest rate is expected to have a negative impact on crude oil prices. Further, due to a lack of availability, this data was manually calculated by subtracting the inflation rate from the nominal interest rate. As oil prices are affected by many exogenous factors, the UK variables are not exhaustive of all crude oil price determinants. Hence, this study also includes a control variable, US GDP, motivated by the literature to act as a proxy for global economic output, sentiment, and overall market conditions.

Model 1 also estimates two dummy variables: D1 for the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) and D2 the 2014/15 oil price collapse. The first is motivated by its wide use in the literature, with Salem et al. (2022) including it in their study finding it had statistically significant effects in both the short- and long-run. On the other hand, the 2014/15 oil price collapse has not been widely used in previous studies, yet its effects were severe (see Figure 1). Model 2 includes the BUI, while Model 3 includes the COVID variable, measuring the number of newly reported COVID-19 cases in the UK. This study uses monthly data due to some variables having limited availability, meaning that, if not reported monthly, data is transformed to show month-end values. The descriptive statistics for each variable, correlation matrices, and sources for all data can be found in the appendix.

4.2 Model Justification

The ARDL approach of Pesaran et al. (2001) has recently gained attention from researchers due to its distinct advantages over other cointegration approaches (Salem et al., 2022). Firstly, ARDL models are highly flexible, allowing the use of small data samples. Models 2 and 3 in this study only capture approximately 35 observations, making the ARDL framework applicable. Further, variables can be integrated of order 0, order 1, or a mix of both. Since a wide range of variables are used in this dissertation, with differing orders of integration, this characteristic is highly beneficial. Finally, ARDL modelling allows for the simultaneous estimation of short- and long-run coefficients, presenting the full picture of the UK's role in oil markets.

One drawback of ARDL modelling is the assumption of symmetry. NARDL models (Shin et al., 2014) relax this assumption, allowing for positive and negative shocks from the independent variables to be tested. Kumar et al. (2021) cite most financial time series to exhibit nonlinearities, making the NARDL approach highly important for a study such as this. NARDL modelling is also highly flexible, exhibiting the same characteristics as ARDL models.

Defining the model in long-run reduced form specification, where α represents the constant term and ε_t represents the error term:

$$OP_t = \alpha + \beta_1 FTSE_t + \beta_2 FX_t + \beta_3 EPU_t + \beta_4 interest_t + \beta_5 GDP_t + \beta_6 BUI_t + \beta_7 COVID_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Model 1 restricts the β_6 and β_7 coefficients to zero. Models 2 and 3 then include the β_6 and β_7 coefficients respectively, allowing for comparisons across these periods of economic uncertainty.

4.3 ARDL Models

After ensuring all variables are integrated of order I(0) or I(1) using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, a prerequisite of ARDL modelling, the study proceeds to transform equation (1) into an error correction format. This is applicable for analysing both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships among the variables. Further, this form easily allows for the error correction term ECT_{t-1} , which is the adjustment process of $\Delta \ln(OP)$ toward the long-run equilibrium, to be viewed.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta \ln(OP) = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \varphi_{OP,j} \Delta \ln(OP)_{t-j} + \sum_{k_1=1}^{q_1-1} \varphi_{FTSE,k_1} \Delta \ln(FTSE)_{t-k_1} + \\
& \sum_{k_2=1}^{q_2-1} \varphi_{FX,k_2} \Delta \ln(FX)_{t-k_2} + \sum_{k_3=1}^{q_3-1} \varphi_{EPU,k_3} \Delta \ln(EPU)_{t-k_3} + \\
& \sum_{k_4=1}^{q_4-1} \varphi_{interest,k_4} \Delta \ln(interest)_{t-k_4} + \sum_{k_5=1}^{q_5-1} \varphi_{GDP,k_5} \Delta \ln(GDP)_{t-k_5} + \\
& \sum_{k_6=1}^{q_6-1} \varphi_{BUI,k_6} \Delta \ln(BUI)_{t-k_6} + \sum_{k_7=1}^{q_7-1} \varphi_{COVID,k_7} \Delta \ln(COVID)_{t-k_7} + \lambda_{OP} \ln(OP)_{t-1} + \\
& \lambda_{FTSE} \ln(FTSE)_{t-1} + \lambda_{FX} \ln(FX)_{t-1} + \lambda_{EPU} \ln(EPU)_{t-1} + \lambda_{interest} interest_{t-1} + \\
& \lambda_{GDP} \ln(GDP)_{t-1} + \lambda_{BUI} BUI_{t-1} + \lambda_{COVID} \ln(COVID)_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

Equation (2) presents an $ARDL(p, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6, q_7)$ model, where crude oil price enters as an autoregressive process of order p and the independent variables enter as symmetrically distributed lag variables of order $q_1, \dots, q_7$. The equation can be broken down to show the short-run dynamics $\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \varphi_{OP,j} \Delta \ln(OP)_{t-j} + \dots + \sum_{k_7=1}^{q_7-1} \varphi_{COVID,k_7} \Delta \ln(COVID)_{t-k_7}$ and long-run equilibrium $\lambda_{OP} \ln(OP)_{t-1} + \dots + \lambda_{COVID} \ln(COVID)_{t-1}$. The latter allows for the error correction term to be interpreted. Should this term fall between -1 and 0, and be statistically significant, a long-run cointegrating relationship is inferred.

Pesaran et al. (2001) offer five alternative methods of presenting this model, depending on how the deterministic terms (trend and intercept) are treated. This study makes the simplifying assumption to use the restricted constant trend specification, Case (II), as this is used in the majority of ARDL studies with oil price as the dependent variable (see Kisswani, 2021; Salem et al., 2022). The use of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is also common practice across the literature, therefore this study will select the optimal lag order using this criterion.

All three ARDL models set maximum lags to three as it is rare to see more than four lags used for this type of modelling due to the principle of parsimony^[1]. After obtaining the short-term coefficients, the presence of serial correlation among the residuals is tested using the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test. The null hypothesis states that the residuals are free from serial correlation, and is rejected if the associated p-value is less than 5% significance. If the model is without serial correlation, the lag lengths are deemed appropriate and ARDL modelling can continue.

The presence of a cointegrating relationship is then assessed using an F-test, evaluating the joint significance of the coefficients associated with the lagged variables. Pesaran et al. (2001) proposed new critical values to account for the level of integration amongst the variables, depending on the case assumed and the number of variables being modelled. The null hypothesis states that there is no cointegrating relationship in the model, and is rejected when the associated p-value is less than 5% significance. Therefore, the model specification must be re-evaluated should the null fail to be rejected. It is noteworthy that the models without the control variable GDP_t failed to reject the null hypothesis of cointegration, deeming the long-run coefficients to be not meaningful and supporting the rationale behind including this variable.

Finally, the associated cumulative sum (CUSUM) tests are plotted to assess the stability of the coefficients over their respective sample periods. The CUSUM plot is compared against 5% critical values to determine if there is evidence of a structural change in a model's variables. If the plot breaks the critical levels, instability can be inferred. Salem et al. (2022) do not report tests for stability in their study, limiting the robustness of their results.

[1] The parsimony principle states that, in statistics, models with fewer parameters are favoured over more complex models, hence only three lags (months) are considered in this paper.

4.4 NARDL Models

In the above ARDL specification, it is assumed that the effects of the explanatory variables on oil prices are symmetric. For a model examining oil prices this is a major limitation, with the nature of financial data suggesting nonlinear models are more appropriate. Further, nonlinear modelling allows the directional effects of variables on oil prices to be captured. Illustrating this in an example, assume that the UK interest rate rises by 2%. Theoretically, this would cause a decrease in demand for crude oil prices, depressing prices. The same downward pressure would not be expected if the UK real interest rate fell by 2%. In other words, the magnitude of a rise in real interest rates is not equal to that of a fall. The linear framework is inappropriate to investigate such asymmetric changes (Salem et al., 2022), in some cases not capturing a full set of results.

Shin et al. (2014) proposed a nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) framework where nonlinearities, both in the short- and long-run, can be modelled as positive and negative partial sum decompositions, showing the impact of directional shocks. This dissertation applies this method to investigate the nonlinear effects of the chosen variables on crude oil prices. Following Shin et al. (2014), any variable x_t can be decomposed as $x_t = x_0 + x_t^+ + x_t^-$ where x_0 is its initial value, and x_t^+ , x_t^- are the partial sum processes of positive and negative changes to x_t . Treating x_t as the explanatory variables outlined in (1), the following partial sum decompositions are derived:

$$\begin{aligned}
 FTSE_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta FTSE_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta FTSE_i, 0); \\
 FTSE_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta FTSE_{i=1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta FTSE_i, 0) \\
 FX_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta FX_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta FX_i, 0); \\
 FX_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta FX_{i=1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta FX_i, 0) \\
 EPU_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta EPU_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta EPU_i, 0); \\
 EPU_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta EPU_{i=1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta EPU_i, 0) \\
 interest_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta interest_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta interest_i, 0); \\
 interest_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta interest_{i=1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta interest_i, 0) \\
 GDP_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta GDP_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta GDP_i, 0); \\
 GDP_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta GDP_{i=1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta GDP_i, 0) \\
 BUI_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta BUI_{i=1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta BUI_i, 0);
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
BUI_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta BUI_{i-1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta BUI_i, 0) \\
COVID_t^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta COVID_{i-1}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta COVID_i, 0); \\
COVID_t^- &= \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta COVID_{i-1}^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta COVID_i, 0)
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Then by substituting the definitions of these partial sums into equation (2), the nonlinear conditional error correction model is derived:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta \ln(OP) &= \alpha_1 + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \varphi_{OP,j} \Delta \ln(OP)_{t-j} + \sum_{k_1=1}^{q_1-1} (\varphi_{FTSE,k_1}^+ \Delta \ln(FTSE)_{t-k_1}^+ + \\
&\varphi_{FTSE,k_1}^- \Delta \ln(FTSE)_{t-k_1}^-) + \sum_{k_2=1}^{q_2-1} (\varphi_{FX,k_2}^+ \Delta \ln(FX)_{t-k_2}^+ + \varphi_{FX,k_2}^- \Delta \ln(FX)_{t-k_2}^-) + \\
&\sum_{k_3=1}^{q_3-1} (\varphi_{EPU,k_3}^+ \Delta \ln(EPU)_{t-k_3}^+ + \varphi_{EPU,k_3}^- \Delta \ln(EPU)_{t-k_3}^-) + \\
&\sum_{k_4=1}^{q_4-1} (\varphi_{interest,k_4}^+ \Delta interest_{t-k_4}^+ + \varphi_{interest,k_4}^- \Delta interest_{t-k_4}^-) + \\
&\sum_{k_5=1}^{q_5-1} (\varphi_{GDP,k_5}^+ \Delta \ln(GDP)_{t-k_5}^+ + \varphi_{GDP,k_5}^- \Delta \ln(GDP)_{t-k_5}^-) + \sum_{k_6=1}^{q_6-1} (\varphi_{BUI,k_6}^+ \Delta BUI_{t-k_6}^+ + \\
&\varphi_{BUI,k_6}^- \Delta BUI_{t-k_6}^-) + \sum_{k_7=1}^{q_7-1} (\varphi_{COVID,k_7}^+ \Delta \ln(COVID)_{t-k_7}^+ + \varphi_{COVID,k_7}^- \Delta \ln(COVID)_{t-k_7}^-) + \\
&\lambda_{OP} \ln(OP)_{t-1} + \lambda_{FTSE}^+ \ln(FTSE)_{t-1}^+ + \lambda_{FTSE}^- \ln(FTSE)_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{FX}^+ \ln(FX)_{t-1}^+ + \\
&\lambda_{FX}^- \ln(FX)_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{EPU}^+ \ln(EPU)_{t-1}^+ + \lambda_{EPU}^- \ln(EPU)_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{interest}^+ interest_{t-1}^+ + \\
&\lambda_{interest}^- interest_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{GDP}^+ \ln(GDP)_{t-1}^+ + \lambda_{GDP}^- \ln(GDP)_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{BUI}^+ BUI_{t-1}^+ + \\
&\lambda_{BUI}^- BUI_{t-1}^- + \lambda_{COVID}^+ \ln(COVID)_{t-1}^+ + \lambda_{COVID}^- \ln(COVID)_{t-1}^- + \varepsilon_t
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Having already tested that the variables are either integrated of order I(0) or I(1), the model will be estimated following the iterative NARDL estimation approach in EViews 13 (IHSEViews, 2022). All explanatory variables are initially treated as having a joint (long- and short-run) asymmetric effect on crude oil prices. The maximum lags are then set to two for model 1, but are restricted to one for models 2&3 due to a limited number of observations. This is a clear limitation of this study, with future opportunities for research that has a larger sample size, perhaps daily data, and therefore higher maximum lag orders. The optimal lag order with the lowest AIC is then selected.

The first inferential exercise aims to validate the assumptions of asymmetry in the primary model specification. While initially assuming asymmetry in both the long- and short-run for all variables, NARDL modelling is adaptable to partial asymmetry, for instance a variable is asymmetric only in the short-run. Each variable in (4) has associated asymmetric level

coefficients λ^+ , λ^- , as well as difference coefficients φ_k^+ , φ_k^- . Formally defining the coefficient symmetry test used:

Long-run symmetry only $H_0 : \lambda^+ = \lambda^-$

Short-run symmetry only $H_0 : \begin{cases} \varphi_k^+ = \varphi_k^- \text{ for each } k \\ \text{or} \\ \sum_{k=1}^q \varphi_{k=1}^+ = \sum_{k=1}^q \varphi_{k=1}^- \end{cases}$

Joint Long- and Short-run symmetry $H_0 : \begin{cases} \varphi_k^+ = \varphi_k^- \text{ for each } k \text{ and } \lambda^+ = \lambda^- \\ \text{or} \\ \sum_{k=1}^q \varphi_{k=1}^+ = \sum_{k=1}^q \varphi_{k=1}^- \text{ and } \lambda^+ = \lambda^- \end{cases}$

H_0 is rejected if the associated p-value from the symmetry test is less than 5%, indicating that there is sufficient evidence to conclude asymmetry between the given independent variable and crude oil price. Depending on the output from this primary test, the model is adjusted to reflect whether each variable is asymmetric in the short-run, long-run, or joint case. If there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypotheses, the variable will be treated as a standard regressor (symmetric) in the second iteration, as in the ARDL approach. Additionally, should the variable enter with zero lags, it also is treated as symmetric since the test's results are inconclusive (NA), showing the limitation associated with having a maximum lag order $(p, q) = (1, 1)$.

The new model is then estimated, returning a different optimal lag ordering and a new set of symmetry test results that are used to validate the changes made before estimating this iteration. Further, the AIC criteria of each iteration are considered. Having selected the model with the better fit, the F-bounds statistics are calculated, as in the linear case, to determine the existence and direction of long-run coefficients.

Another advantage of NARDL models is that dynamic multiplier graphs can be plotted, an extension to the work of Salem et al. (2022). These graphs are similar to IRFs, tracking the non-linear adjustment paths of each explanatory variable towards its cointegrating state in the short-run (Shin et al. 2014).

5 Empirical Results and Discussion

This section will describe the results obtained following the methodology outlined in section 4, having used Microsoft Excel for data manipulation and EViews 13 for ARDL and NARDL estimations.

5.1 Examining the Raw Data

Figure 1 shows significant variations in crude oil prices, driven by major economic events. The largest drawdown of prices was during the GFC, justifying its inclusion in the model as a dummy variable. Figure 1 also highlights the oil price crash of 2014-2016, mostly caused by a supply glut from booming oil production and receding geopolitical tensions. Further, OPEC's announcement of aiming to improve its market share of oil in November 2014 was interpreted as an aggressive move, attempting to squeeze higher-cost producers, such as US shale oil, out of the market (Behar and Ritz, 2016). This crash is not included in previous studies, despite being highly influential on Brent Crude prices (see Figure 1). Finally, the periods of Brexit and COVID are also depicted, showing periods of volatility.

Figure 1: Monthly Brent Crude Oil Price (USD). January 2001 – December 2022

The UK variables in Figure 2 demonstrate similar characteristics as the majority of fluctuations occur around the same economic events. This emphasises the need to segment different periods. For example, the period following the initial COVID-19 shock saw real interest rates plummet, as well as oil prices, to unprecedented lows. The FTSE 100 and EPU indices show upward trends, however experience significant levels of noise. Further, although GBP/USD and real interest rates are downward trending, there are also significant levels of volatility. Hence, all variables in this study undergo logarithmic transformations, except for real interest rates as these fall below zero; potentially a limitation of this analysis.

Figure 2: Monthly FTSE 100 Closing Price (Top Left); Monthly GBP/USD Exchange Rate (Top Right); Monthly UK EPU Index (Bottom Left); Monthly UK Real Interest Rate (Bottom Right)

5.2 Short-Run ARDL Results

Table 1 depicts the ARDL results in the short-run for all three models. In Model 1, the short-run coefficient associated with FTSE is significant at the 1% level, indicating that the FTSE 100 index has a statistically significant impact on crude oil prices in the short-term. Further, the coefficient is positive and enters the model with zero lags, suggesting that fluctuations in the FTSE 100 index can lead to immediate increases in oil prices. This confirms the conclusions made by Tang and Xiong (2012) and Cheng and Xiong (2014) of financialisation in the oil market creating a more dynamic relationship between the stock and oil markets. However, Models 2&3 imply that this relationship is inverse in the short-run during periods of

uncertainty, supporting Abuzayed et al. (2022) who claimed oil to be a strong inflation hedge when consumer sentiment is low.

Table 1: Short-Run Coefficients of Linear ARDL Models

Code	Model 1				Model 2				Model 3			
	Number of Lags				Number of Lags				Number of Lags			
	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3
<i>log(ftse)</i>	0.2489**				1.1076*	-2.1013**	0.9243	-0.7436	2.0048	-0.7239	1.3578*	-1.3117*
<i>log(fx)</i>	1.1796**	-0.7909**			1.5486*	0.2481	1.2826*		0.0877			
<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.0227*				-0.0555*	0.0372	-0.0202		-0.0473			
<i>interest</i>	-5.0284*	5.6288	-3.6552		-14.2832	-0.8198	0.8213	19.3922**	1.7164	-3.4007		
<i>log(gdp)</i>	5.7319**	-2.7729	0.1327	-2.9045*	9.5977*	-0.4875	-5.6841		-3.8159*	1.1595	-1.6186	-2.1450*
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	-	-	0.7383	1.0308*	-2.252**		-	-	-	-
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0377	-0.0223	0.0467*	
<i>D1</i>	0.0531	-0.1106	0.1498*		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>D2</i>	-0.0970**				-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

The short-run coefficient associated with interest is also statistically significant in Model 1, exhibiting a negative relationship at recommended lag 1. This mirrors the theoretical model proposed by Hotelling (1931), as well as the majority of empirical studies discussed in the literature review. Model 2 also yields a statistically significant coefficient, however, suggests that interest rate fluctuations positively affect oil price. Arora and Tanner (2013) provide a potential explanation for this, only finding an inverse relationship between interest rate and oil price if the sample goes through the mid-2000s, meaning that this model potentially suffers from sample bias as it spans just three years. Further, Model 3 fails to conclude a statistically significant relationship between interest rate and oil price, which is synonymous with Salem et al. (2022)'s results, observing a drop-off in significant variables when assessing the COVID model.

The contradictory signs of the FX coefficients between Model 1 and Model 2 underscore the need to assess nonlinear dynamics between FX and oil prices. The unexpected negative coefficient in model 1, indicating that a domestic currency appreciation leads to a decrease in oil prices, contradicts predictions given that oil is typically traded in USD. Theoretically, a higher purchasing power of Sterling against the Dollar would increase UK oil demand and drive up prices. Further inference is needed from the NARDL models in this case.

As for the control variable, its sign suggests an inverse relationship between GDP and crude oil price for most lags. As this model uses GDP as a proxy for global economic activity, these results go against the literature (see Wang and Sun, 2017). One explanation of this is the recent shift to green energy. As countries observe an increase in GDP, they begin to invest more into renewable energies than in previous years, which could drive the price of crude oil down. Further, since US data is used to measure GDP in this model, this effect is likely magnified. The US has ranked first in the Renewable Energy Country Attractiveness Index (RECAI) for most of the last decade (Giovanni and Warren, 2023), meaning they are investing the most into renewable energy, especially since the introduction of the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA)^[2]. Consequently, the choice to include US GDP as the control variable may have been questionable.

The EPU index was found to be statistically significant in the short-run in model 1, but insignificant in model 3, unlike Salem et al. (2022) who observed a weakly significant negative coefficient in their model with COVID, but no significance for the sample without COVID. This suggests that the UK's EPU is more closely linked to oil price than in the US during periods of lower uncertainty, which is counterintuitive since higher periods of economic uncertainty, such as during Brexit and COVID, should inversely impact oil prices, which are sensitive to negative news. Nevertheless, the BUI variable emerged as highly statistically significant in model 2. The BUI variable operates similarly to EPU, but is more relevant to model 2 as it is specific to Brexit uncertainty rather than general policy uncertainty. Consequently, specific uncertainty indices such as this one are shown to be of high importance.

The COVID coefficient in model 3 suggests a positive relationship between the number of reported UK COVID-19 cases and crude oil prices. This contradicts the findings of Salem et al. (2022), who observe a negative short-term relationship and explain this is also due to economic uncertainty. Further, the coefficients of the two dummy variables imply that the 2014/15 oil price crash had a more immediate negative impact than the GFC. Overall, comparing model 1 to models 2&3, a reduction in statistically significant short-run coefficients is observed. This implies that during times of major uncertainty the dynamics of oil prices are irregular. The same conclusion is reached by Salem et al. (2022). Consequently, the implications for both policymakers and investors differ depending on the state of the economy.

[2] The IRA, implemented by US President Joe Biden, aims to reduce inflation, drastically expanding subsidies to green technology companies (Brashers, 2023). This is likely to place downward pressure on crude oil prices.

Additionally, this emphasises the need to study the nonlinear relationships to gain a more comprehensive understanding of oil price movements as linear modelling has become inefficient; as hypothesised by the literature.

5.3 Long-Run ARDL Results

The estimated coefficients for the long-run relationship in the linear ARDL models are shown in Table 2. Model 1 shows that all variables except US GDP are statistically significant. The sign of FX is as predicted, concluding that, on the demand side, a relative depreciation in the dollar increases oil imports from other countries, in this case the UK, placing upward pressure on oil price. This is in accordance with Frankel (2003) and Coudert et al. (2008). The only statistically significant result in Model 2 is FX, suggesting during Brexit this relationship is likely to be amplified due to increased uncertainty and evolving trade relationships.

Table 2: Long-Run Coefficient Estimates of Linear ARDL Models

Code	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Coefficient	T-statistic	Coefficient	T-statistic	Coefficient	T-statistic
<i>log(ftse)</i>	1.2525**	4.2547	-2.0616	-0.6567	8.4524	0.8583
<i>log(fx)</i>	1.9558**	4.7662	7.8085**	3.9108	0.5583	0.0970
<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.1141*	-2.0005	-0.0975	-0.9384	-0.3015	-0.6468
<i>interest</i>	-15.3705**	-7.3983	12.9590	1.0208	-10.7275	-0.5497
<i>log(gdp)</i>	0.9425	1.0369	8.6878	1.3982	-40.8899	-0.7326
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	-1.2245	-1.1364	-	-
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	-	-	0.3957	0.7882
<i>D1</i>	0.4647**	3.3457				
<i>D2</i>	-0.4881**	-3.1778				
Diagnostic Statistics Associated with Linear ARDL Models 1-3						
<i>ECT_t-1</i>	-0.1987**	-7.0195	-0.3944**	-9.8850	-0.1570**	-10.8025
<i>F-stat</i>	5.2245**		7.1848**		9.7245**	
<i>LM Test</i>	0.1723	Prob.= 0.8419	3.7718	Prob.=0.0702	1.4478	Prob.= 0.2734

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

Model 1 also suggests that the FTSE, EPU, and interest variables are all statistically significant. The signs are coherent with the short-run results, implying that these variables have persistent effects on oil prices over time, enhancing the justification to include them in models and analyses aimed at understanding oil market fluctuations. Both dummy variables are also statistically significant at the 1% level, whereas Salem et al. (2022) found no evidence of a significant relationship between the GFC. This suggests that the UK is structurally different to the US and is affected differently, emphasising the need for research into country-specific

impacts on oil, rather than generalised studies. Further, accounting for the 2015 oil price crash proved important when assessing for changes in oil price. The model including COVID exhibits no statistically significant relationships. The same conclusion is drawn from Salem et al. (2022)'s study, again highlighting the need for nonlinear relationships to be studied.

Table 2 also displays a sample of inferential diagnostic tests such as F-statistics from the Bounds Test, the Error Correction Term (ECT), and results from the LM Test. In all models, the F-statistic is larger than the upper bound $I(1)$ at the 1% level, meaning there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration, hence the long-run coefficients are meaningful. The values of the bounds themselves are reported by Pesaran et al. (2001), and are reliant on the number of variables given in the selected model, as well as the case chosen. This study assumes case (II) for all models, and fixes $k = 7$ in model 1, and $k = 6$ in models 2&3; where k is the number of independent variables. The results from the LM test in all three models are insignificant, meaning there is insufficient evidence to reject the null, confirming the residuals are free from autocorrelation.

The ECT in Model 1 is negative with an estimated coefficient of -0.1987. This negative coefficient suggests that approximately 19.87% of any deviation from the long-run equilibrium is corrected within one period. Further, the associated t-statistic of -5.2919 implies that this coefficient is highly significant, meaning that oil prices converge back to their equilibrium level relatively quickly following shocks. Kisswani (2021) finds a similar coefficient in his study examining how uncertainty affects WTI oil price. The ECTs in Models 2&3 are also significantly negative with absolute values below one, as required for a long-run cointegrating relationship. Model 2 has the largest magnitude ECT, indicating the fastest adjustment process toward equilibrium during the Brexit period, whilst Model 3 has the lowest magnitude ECT. This suggests that market participants were quicker to respond to Brexit uncertainties than they were to COVID-19 concerns.

Finally, as an extension to previous literature, this study assesses the stability of the coefficients estimated for lagged variables and the ECT. Figure 3 plots the cumulative sum of the estimated coefficients over time, showing the relationships to be stable if the CUSUM graph remains within the 5% significance bounds. For the most part, the three models do not exhibit any structural breaks, the only exception being a minor shift in Model 3. As this deviation is so

insignificant, there is not sufficient evidence to conclude instability in the model. Consequently, the estimations from the ARDL models in the short- and long-run are shown to be robust.

Figure 3: ARDL CUSUM Plots; 5% significance bands

5.4 NARDL Results

Table 3 shows the results from treating each variable as having a joint asymmetric impact on oil price in model 1; the first iteration of the NARDL approach used in this study.

Table 3: Model 1 NARDL(2,0,2,2,2,1,2,0) - Full Asymmetry

Short-Run (1st Iteration)			Long-Run (1st Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests				
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Short-Run		Long-Run		
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob	F-stat	Prob
<i>log(ftse)+</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)+</i>	0.0431	0.1915	<i>log(ftse)</i>	NA		0.2846	0.5945
<i>log(fx)+</i>	0.4891	-1.1139*	<i>log(ftse)-</i>	0.1915	1.7721	<i>log(fx)</i>	8.2758**	0.0046	0.3227	0.5708
<i>log(fx)-</i>	1.9020**	0.9589*	<i>log(fx)+</i>	0.3099	0.8073	<i>log(epu)</i>	1.0930	0.2974	2.4012	0.1233
<i>log(epu)+</i>	-0.0144	-0.0329	<i>log(fx)-</i>	0.632*	2.2320	<i>interest</i>	1.8876	0.1715	1.3833	0.2414
<i>log(epu)-</i>	-0.0467*	0.0491*	<i>log(epu)+</i>	-0.0192	-0.1016	<i>log(gdp)</i>	0.0428	0.8363	1.5485	0.2152
<i>interest+</i>	-6.1108	-2.8847	<i>log(epu)-</i>	-0.0380	-1.8911	Associated Diagnostic Statistics				
<i>interest-</i>	-5.7428	9.8388**	<i>interest+</i>	-1.0324	-0.5648	Test				
<i>log(gdp)+</i>	5.2543*		<i>interest-</i>	-4.9891*	-2.4262	F-Stat	2.8713			
<i>log(gdp)-</i>	4.4399		<i>log(gdp)+</i>	-0.3124	-0.3018	LM Test	1.443 Prob=0.2394			
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	<i>log(gdp)-</i>	1.7901	1.2410	AIC	-2.1044			
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	<i>brexit</i>	-	-	Adj. R^2	0.4158			
D1	0.0455	-0.1686*	<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	ECT_t-1	-0.2271**			
D2	NA		D1	0.0424	1.0334					
			D2	-0.1109**	-3.1362					

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

The symmetry test rejects the null hypothesis of symmetry in the short-run for FX, whilst FTSE cannot be evaluated since it enters this model with zero lags. All other variables cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. This suggests that equation (3) must be adapted by removing the partial sum decompositions of: FTSE, EPU, real interest, and GDP.

The new results in Table 4 reinforce the conclusion that *FX* is partially asymmetric in the short-run at the 1% significance level. Further, by comparing the associated diagnostic statistics between the first (full asymmetry) and second (partial asymmetry) NARDL iterations, it is evident that the partial asymmetry model is more robust. The F-bounds test statistic now beyond the I(1) critical value, when it was not in the first iteration, meaning long-run coefficients are more meaningful. Further, the AIC criteria are approximately equal. Analysis for model 1 is therefore favoured using the NARDL(2,0,2,1,2,1,2,0) model.

Table 4: Model 1 NARDL(2,0,2,1,2,1,2,0) - Partial Asymmetry

Short-Run (2nd Iteration)			Long-Run (2nd Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests		
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Short-Run		
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob
<i>log(ftse)</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)</i>	0.1985**	2.7106	<i>log(fx)</i>	9.5700**	0.0023
<i>log(fx)+</i>	0.5340	-1.1231*	<i>log(fx)</i>	0.4256**	3.3821			
<i>log(fx)-</i>	1.8375**	1.0538*	<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.0098	-0.7822	Associated Diagnostic Statistics		
<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.0266*		<i>interest</i>	-3.0489**	-4.0813	Test		
<i>interest</i>	-5.4200**	4.3587*	<i>log(gdp)</i>	0.2801	1.5330	F-Stat	4.6024**	
<i>log(gdp)</i>	4.6209**		<i>brexit</i>	-	-	LM Test	1.5376 Prob=0.2180	
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	AIC	-2.1586	
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	D1	0.0672**		Adj. R^2	0.4183	
D1	0.0642	-0.1648**	D2	-0.0869**		ECT_t-1	-0.2035**	
D2	NA							

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

The same process was repeated for the models containing Brexit and COVID-19. Model 2 produced favourable results in the first iteration, while Model 3 favoured the second iteration. The most robust $NARDL(p, q_1, \dots, q_n)$ models were selected and are presented in Tables 5 and 6 respectively, with their alternative iterations displayed in the Appendix.

Table 5: Model 2 NARDL(1,1,0,0,0,0,0) - Full Asymmetry

Short-Run (1st Iteration)			Long-Run (1st Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests				
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Short-Run		Long-Run		
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob	F-stat	Prob
<i>log(ftse)+</i>	1.7086		<i>log(ftse)+</i>	0.2993	0.3050	<i>log(ftse)</i>	2.0100	0.1725	9.9692**	0.0052
<i>log(ftse)-</i>	3.8105**		<i>log(ftse)-</i>	5.1777**	4.9667					
<i>log(fx)</i>	NA		<i>log(fx)+</i>	2.8196*	2.4987	<i>log(fx)</i>	NA		2.5562	0.1264
<i>log(epu)</i>	NA		<i>log(fx)-</i>	-0.4763	-0.4202	<i>log(epu)</i>	NA		4.2108	0.0542
<i>interest</i>	NA		<i>log(epu)+</i>	0.0069	0.1518	<i>interest</i>	NA		4.0465	0.0587
<i>log(gdp)</i>	NA		<i>log(epu)-</i>	-0.1316**	-3.2168	<i>log(gdp)</i>	NA		3.5789	0.0739
<i>brexit</i>	NA		<i>interest+</i>	49.7465**	3.4588	<i>brexit</i>	NA		0.3778	0.5460
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	<i>interest-</i>	14.8817*	2.4426	Associated Diagnostic Statistics				
D1	-	-	<i>log(gdp)+</i>	-7.9150	-1.1823	Test				
D2	-	-	<i>log(gdp)-</i>	29.9021	1.8896	F-Stat	4.5487**			
			<i>brexit+</i>	-0.2285	-0.4905	LM Test	0.9994 Prob=0.3887			
			<i>brexit-</i>	-0.7817	-0.8750	AIC	-3.0550			
			<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	Adj. R^2	0.6971			
						ECT_t-1	-0.5925			

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

Table 6: Model 3 NARDL(1,0,0,1,1,1,0) - Partial Asymmetry

Short-Run (2nd Iteration)			Long-Run (2nd Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests			
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Short-Run		Long-Run	
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob	F-stat
<i>log(ftse)+</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)+</i>	1.7124**	3.9393	<i>log(ftse)</i>	-	0.7033	0.4121
<i>log(ftse)-</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)-</i>	2.3195*	2.7583	<i>log(ftse)</i>	-		
<i>log(fx)+</i>	NA		<i>log(fx)</i>	-0.2359	-0.2892	<i>log(fx)</i>	NA	-	
<i>log(fx)-</i>	NA		<i>log(epu)</i>	0.0572	1.1777	<i>interest</i>	6.0372*	0.0238	2.7657
<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.0042		<i>interest+</i>	-8.1361	-1.6393	<i>log(gdp)</i>	-		140.4271**
<i>interest+</i>	-8.2376		<i>interest-</i>	-0.6272	-0.3103				
<i>interest-</i>	7.0805*		<i>log(gdp)+</i>	-1.0050	-0.7914				
<i>log(gdp)</i>	-4.3821**		<i>log(gdp)-</i>	-10.9935**	-8.3776				
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	<i>brexit</i>	-	-				
<i>log(covid)</i>	NA		<i>log(covid)</i>	0.0112	0.8661				
						Associated Diagnostic Statistics			
						Test			
						F-Stat	58.8566**		
						LM Test	2.2767 Prob=0.1330		
						AIC	-2.7127		
						Adj. R^2	0.9591		
						ECT_t-1	-0.5326**		

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

Analysing Tables 4-6, each iteration produces an F-Statistic for the bounds test greater than I(1) at the 1% significance level, confirming there is evidence of a long-run relationship in the respective models. Further, all LM tests confirm the absence of serial correlation and all ECTs are less than the absolute value of one.

The selected iteration for Model 1 only sees FX have an asymmetric relationship in the short-run (both positive and negative). In Model 2, under partial asymmetry, only the negative coefficient for FTSE is found to be statistically significant in the short run. Finally, Model 3 shows interest and GDP to have asymmetric effects on oil price. These relationships can be plotted using cumulative dynamic multiplier (CDM) graphs, presenting a visual representation of the adjustment of oil prices to shocks in those asymmetric explanatory variables (Shin et al., 2014). By computing a 95% bootstrap confidence interval with a horizon level $h = 25$, the following CDMs, presented by Figure 4, were created for those four variables rejecting the null hypothesis of the symmetry test.

Positive shocks to OP from FX in Model 1 converge to their long-run limit slower than negative shocks, justifying the significant coefficient of FX^+ at lag one, but not lag zero. However, negative shocks are shown to have a larger impact to OP, suggesting that OP are quicker to respond to relative appreciations in USD. An increasing number of studies have shown exchange rate fluctuations to be nonlinear, with Chinn (1991) attributing this to tighter currency bands and increasing barriers to trade; both inducing extra layers of uncertainty. The

convergence to equilibrium is shown to take place after approximately one year, indicating that while the initial response may differ between positive and negative shocks, the long-run effects eventually stabilize, aligning with the established relationship identified in the ARDL model and literature.

Figure 4: CDM Plots from NARDL Estimations

The effect of FTSE on OP in model 2 shows that negative shocks to the stock market affect OP more than positive ones. This visually shows how, through the financialisation of commodity markets, oil has become a hedge against uncertainty. These shocks converge to their long-run limit quickly, showing the rapid adjustment process from investors buying oil contracts. The asymmetric shocks of real interest rates in model 3 show a decrease in UK real interest rates being associated with a significant rise in oil prices. This adds to the inverse relationship concluded from the ARDL model, showing that interest rate falls are more likely to lead to an impact on oil prices than rate hikes. Their convergence to the long-run limit is also rapid, with both positive and negative shocks causing a decrease in OP in the long-run. The absence of statistically significant coefficients in the long-run confirm the findings of Alquist et al. (2013), who reported a consistent inverse short-run relationship with real interest rates and oil prices, but failed to demonstrate a significant long-run relationship. Finally, negative GDP changes during COVID are shown to have a far greater, and statistically significant,

impact on oil price. Contractionary shocks to economic activity, such as lockdowns and furloughs, led to a rapid and strong decline in OP by the fourth horizon period.

Looking at the three models collectively, and comparing their results to section the ARDL models, the overall number of statistically significant variables rises when nonlinearities are considered. In particular, model 3 saw no significant coefficients in the long-run when following the ARDL framework, but observed the effects of interest and GDP with statistical significance using the NARDL approach. This develops the findings of Salem et al. (2022), who found the same superiority of NARDL modelling using US data.

6 Conclusion

This dissertation aims to assess the major determinants of crude oil prices in the UK, comparing different periods of economic uncertainty such as Brexit and the COVID pandemic. Different relationships were found having used UK data instead of US data, highlighting the importance of country-specific analysis. Further, the rise in statistically significant variables when viewing the NARDL models compared to the ARDL models confirms the view that asymmetries are necessary to consider when modelling financial data. Nonlinear relationships were found to be most common during periods of higher economic uncertainty, with the number of significant variables in the long-run rising from one to three in the Brexit period and zero to two in the COVID period. The estimates from this dissertation imply that periods of uncertainty in the UK economy influence Brent crude oil prices, highlighting several implications for policymakers and investors alike.

6.1 Policy Implications

The results from this study have important policy implications for policymakers. Perhaps most importantly, the UK government should have the capability to quickly and accurately identify oil price shocks to ensure oil price stability. For example, short-run shocks to the GBP/USD exchange rate were shown to be inversely related to oil prices in model 1, before converging to positively related long-run equilibrium. As a net importer of oil, the UK can

capitalise on this relationship by decreasing imports following short-run shocks. Further, the UK government should prioritise monitoring large-scale periods of uncertainty, such as Brexit and COVID-19. Drawing on the exchange rate example again, model 2 showed the “normal” relationship to collapse during the Brexit period, implying that policymakers should adapt when economic uncertainty is high. This can be optimised by governments using domestic uncertainty indices such as the UK EPU or BUI.

Investors should also closely monitor oil price shocks to maximise profits. The inverse relationship captured during periods of uncertainty between the FTSE 100 and crude oil prices implies that investors should hedge stock market uncertainty by buying oil contracts. This monitoring process, for policymakers and investors alike, should be regularly updated to keep up with the quickly evolving oil market. Finally, these implications should not be generalised since they are country-specific. For example, Salem et al. (2022) used US data to find the opposite relationship with exchange rates as oil is traded in USD.

6.2 Limitations and Opportunity for Further Study

Due to daily data not being available for some variables, this study opted to use monthly data, limiting the number of maximum lags that could be applied to some of the models. A study with a larger data set would yield more accurate results, particularly in the NARDL models, as those variables entering with lag order zero could not be assessed for asymmetry. Additionally, more country-specific tests should be performed, particularly for a net exporter of crude oil, to provide an understanding of global oil market dynamics. Finally, a more suitable control variable could be tested in this model, such as the price of futures. It was found that US GDP had an unexpected negative impact on oil prices, attributed to the growing investment into green technology.

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8 Appendices

Appendix 1: Data Presentation

Variables	Description	Definition	Source	Expected Effect
OP	Crude Oil Price (Spot)	Europe Brent Spot Price FOB (Dollars per Barrel)	EIA	NA
FTSE	FTSE 100 Index	Closing price of the FTSE 100 Index on the last day of a given month	investing.com	Positive
FX	GBP/USD Exchange Rate	GBP/USD exchange rate on the last day of a given month	investing.com	Positive
EPU	UK Economic Policy Uncertainty Index	A measure of the degree of uncertainty in an economy; assessing 11 UK newspapers	policyuncertainty.com	Negative
Interest	UK Real Interest Rate	Calculated by subtracting the UK inflation rate from the UK nominal interest rate	ONS & The Bank of England Database	Negative
GDP	US Gross Domestic Product	Used as a proxy for global demand to control exogenous factors	S&P Global Market Intelligence	Positive
BREXIT	Brexit Uncertainty Index	Shows percentage of firms who reported Brexit was in top three major business concerns	Bank of England	Negative
COVID	Number of COVID-19 Cases in UK	Sum of reported COVID-19 cases per month, both first cases and reinfections	gov.uk	Negative

Appendix 2: Descriptive Statistics for Variables

	Observations	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
OP	264	67.26	29.37	14.85	138.40
FTSE	264	5,991.54	1,044.63	3,567.40	7,748.76
FX	264	1.55	0.22	1.12	2.08
EPU	264	283.18	180.89	23.88	1,212.30
Interest	264	-0.37%	2.83%	-8.85%	5.10%
GDP	264	17,755.32	2,195.65	14,114.55	22,058.05
BREXIT	37	43.41%	7.77%	35.01%	58.67%
COVID	36	568,176.50	743,920.67	1.00	3,221,312.00

Appendix 3: Model 1 Correlation Matrix

	OP	FTSE	FX	EPU	Interest	GDP
OP	1.00					
FTSE	0.52	1.00				
FX	0.23	0.04	1.00			
EPU	0.15	-0.05	-0.15	1.00		
Interest	-0.68	-0.22	0.39	-0.23	1.00	
GDP	0.58	0.73	-0.07	0.06	-0.57	1.00

Appendix 4: Model 2 Correlation Matrix

	OP	FTSE	FX	EPU	Interest	GDP	BREXIT
OP	1.00						
FTSE	0.53	1.00					
FX	0.40	0.29	1.00				
EPU	-0.51	-0.02	-0.05	1.00			
Interest	-0.02	-0.53	-0.56	-0.26	1.00		
GDP	0.64	0.23	-0.01	-0.65	0.31	1.00	
BREXIT	0.22	-0.28	-0.32	-0.56	0.59	0.76	1.00

Appendix 5: Model 3 Correlation Matrix

	OP	FTSE	FX	EPU	Interest	GDP	COVID
OP	1.00						
FTSE	0.89	1.00					
FX	-0.19	-0.05	1.00				
EPU	-0.67	-0.66	-0.15	1.00			
Interest	-0.86	-0.76	0.58	0.50	1.00		
GDP	0.81	0.80	-0.04	-0.82	-0.70	1.00	
COVID	0.31	0.38	0.33	-0.15	-0.20	0.36	1.00

Appendix 6: Model 2 NARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) - Partial Asymmetry

Short-Run (2nd Iteration)			Long-Run (2nd Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests		
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Long-Run		
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob
<i>log(ftse)</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)+</i>	1.5013**	2.8256	<i>log(fx)</i>	1.9001	0.1794
<i>log(fx)</i>	NA		<i>log(ftse)-</i>	2.3887**	3.9583			
<i>log(epu)</i>	NA		<i>log(fx)</i>	1.5363**	4.203	Associated Diagnostic Statistics		
<i>interest</i>	NA		<i>log(epu)</i>	-0.0428	-1.6365	Test		
<i>log(gdp)</i>	NA		<i>interest</i>	10.9868**	3.7997	F-Stat	5.0423**	
<i>brexit</i>	NA		<i>log(gdp)</i>	3.591	1.0574	LM Test	1.2545 Prob =0.3026	
<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	<i>brexit</i>	0.3859	1.1480	AIC	-2.6896	
D1	-	-	<i>log(covid)</i>	-	-	Adj. R ²	0.5133	
D2	-	-				ECT_t-1	-0.4472	

1) * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.

Appendix 7: Model 3 NARDL(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0) - Full Asymmetry

Short-Run (1st Iteration)			Long-Run (1st Iteration)			Coefficient Symmetry Tests				
Code	Number of Lags		Code	Coefficient	T-statistic	Long-Run				
	0	1				Code	F-stat	Prob	F-stat	Prob
<i>log(ftse)+</i>	2.4138*		<i>log(ftse)+</i>	1.5482	1.7869	<i>log(ftse)</i>	2.5588	0.1408	5.3592	0.0431
<i>log(ftse)-</i>	4.3984**		<i>log(ftse)-</i>	6.3639*	2.5307	<i>log(fx)</i>	5.5311*	0.0405	4.9212	0.0508
<i>log(fx)+</i>	6.3306		<i>log(fx)+</i>	7.2243*	2.2664	<i>log(epu)</i>	1.7471	0.2157	3.3106	0.0989
<i>log(fx)-</i>	-3.9054		<i>log(fx)-</i>	-8.5955	-1.9506	<i>interest</i>	9.8713*	0.0105	6.6106*	0.0278
<i>log(epu)+</i>	-0.0707		<i>log(epu)+</i>	0.0041	0.0468	<i>log(gdp)</i>	1.8697	0.2015	15.9054**	0.0026
<i>log(epu)-</i>	0.1167		<i>log(epu)-</i>	0.2441*	2.6874	<i>log(covid)</i>	NA		0.3978	0.5424
<i>interest+</i>	-21.9276*		<i>interest+</i>	-30.9347*	-2.8606	Associated Diagnostic Statistics				
<i>interest-</i>	6.2266		<i>interest-</i>	2.1577	0.5624	Test				
<i>log(gdp)+</i>	-4.6900		<i>log(gdp)+</i>	1.3653	0.5629	F-Stat	17.1784**			
<i>log(gdp)-</i>	0.7072		<i>log(gdp)-</i>	-8.3227**	-3.8380	LM Test	3.2660 Prob =0.0918			
<i>brexit</i>	-	-	<i>brexit</i>	-	-	AIC	-2.8563			
<i>log(covid)</i>	NA		<i>log(covid)+</i>	0.0249	0.7618	Adj. R ²	0.9604			
D1	-	-	<i>log(covid)-</i>	-0.0229	-0.4448	ECT_t-1	-0.8800**			
D2	-	-								

Note: * and ** represent significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively.